

THE MAIN FEATURES OF WRITING FOR SOCIAL ACTION

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ABSTRACT

The article deals with the main features of writing for social action. Actions are affected by the behavior of other sociological creature and according to them decided their activity.

In this article we are going to find out the main characteristics of writing for social action and in order to recapitulate the main factors of writing in social action and the role of writing in teaching foreign languages.

Facione divided teaching writing into five skills: interpretation, analysis, evaluation, inference, and explanation. Later he added the sixth skill self-regulation as the ability to evaluate one's own process of reasoning, utilizing analysis skills, and through questioning, correcting and validating one's results (Facione, 1998). Pupils were engaged in lessons and writing tasks that enhanced their ability to apply these skills. The scores were valued on a scale from 1 (poor) to 4 (very good) based on Facione and Facione (1994) scoring rubric. Ennis found six elements which constitute teaching writing (1996), known as FRISCO: Focus, Reasons, Inference, Situation, Clarity and Overview. In approaching any situation, pupils have to be focused by identifying the main arguments or

problem as guidance for pupils not to get distracted during the thinking process. After bearing in mind the main idea, they can proceed to see the reasons behind the main idea and decide its acceptability (Ennis, 1996). Carter, Bishop, and Kravits (2007) described teaching writing as the process of collecting information, analysing it in different ways, and evaluating the objective of gaining understanding, solving a problem, or making a decision. Rankin (1999) confirmed this, saying that good searchers show the ability to evaluate critically the information they are looking for and apply their judgment to the search process. However, Wade (1995) identifies eight characteristics of teaching writing. From his viewpoint, teaching writing involves asking questions, defining a problem, examining evidence, analysing assumptions and biases, avoiding emotional reasoning, avoiding oversimplification, considering other interpretations, and tolerating ambiguity.

Glock (1986) suggests ways that teachers can reinforce verbal teaching writing skills by focusing greater attention on pupils' "why" questions than their "who," "where" and "how" questions. Teachers should also review their own methods of asking questions, questioning answers, and questioning questions, by performing some of the following techniques:

- When a student asks a "why" question, have the rest of the class discuss the kinds of questions that are most powerful and the sources of their power. Explain the structure of analytical questions. Use such questions especially those generated by pupils in quizzes.
- After pupils are accustomed to answering analytical questions using in-class materials, ask similar questions that they must answer via their own work experience or out-of-class inquiries.
- Have pupils analyse the information presented in the textbook to discern which forms of inquiry were used to generate it.
- Have pupils read critical analyses of their text, and encourage pupils to develop their own criticisms based on their personal experiences.
- Compare opposing positions on a topic, and help pupils identify the sources of the differences of opinion. Avoid emotion-laden topics until pupils begin to perceive the "universality of reinterpretation and redefinition."

In another example, Tripp's (1990) second-year oral communications course pupils' (1) select, define, and establish the parameters of a school-related problem; (2) analyse the problem to identify underlying causes, its scope and seriousness, and potential impact; (3) conduct a brainstorming session to generate creative solutions; (4) assess the proposed solutions in terms of viability and potential effectiveness; (5) reach consensus on

the solutions; and (6) implement the decision. This process helps to develop pupils' group research projects, including producing a technical report based on these efforts, where all student, group members participate in the talking, listening, gathering data, writing and editing portions of these reports. Pupils need to acquire critical evaluation skills which enable them to identify information that meets their needs. To achieve this, pupils were encouraged to compare and contrast different information using criteria including questioning the accuracy "Is this information accurate?", authority "Who is the author?", objectivity "Is the information biased?", authenticity "Is the information authentic?", timeliness "Is the information current?", relevance "Is the information helpful?", and efficiency "Is this information worth the effort?" (Kuhlthau, 2004). The key point is to start developing ideas about what makes up a 'good' or 'sound' argument in a piece of reading, or our own writing, and what criteria we need to apply to test this. Teaching writing requires detective-like skills of persistence to examine and re-examine an argument, in order to take in all the angles and weigh up evidence on every side. To think critically is never to take something on 'face value' but to question and think independently about an issue, however 'authoritative' a writer or thinker may be. Critical analysis is a key activity in evaluation. Evaluation is about weighing up the strengths and weaknesses of an argument in order to decide how much it contributes to a particular body of knowledge in your subject.

Accordingly, the researcher used David R. Heise and Max Weber's assumption and analyses. According to Max Weber, human are performing any time any action in reference of their need. Max Weber considered an important unit of actors in editing of social actions. When an actor performs any type of work then it is action. For this, it is necessary

that it have vested the personal interest of actors at the time of actions. By which many persons are affected or get some sense. [2.4]

If we deliberated the above definition of sociology by Max Weber then these can be describe different type of specialties.

- a. Social Action
- b. Interpretation of Social Action
- c. Causal relationship of course and results of Social Action

To clear the above interpretation Weber writes that action can be say social action in which actor changed their action to think about the others action. In brief, it called social action.

Characteristics of Social Action: Max Weber tells those specialties of social action which can briefly divided in following parts: [3.7]

1. Only action cannot say sociological action.

According to Weber an activity can only be called as social activity in which the action is affected by others people of society. That affect can be three types-

- a. Social action are affected by the action of past. In other words the seed of today's action is hidden in past.
- b. Social action could also being the result of today's behavior.
- c. Social action has future based result so people perform any action today their affect can find in the future life.

2. As written above that the action of single person cannot say sociological action. The only activity can be called social activities, which are affected from others. So in brief, other person is necessary for sociological action. In the reference of other people, social action is transacting.

3. The third specialty of social action is that it is perform affected with others. When person performs action affected the behaviors of other.

4. Sociological activities are inter-related. Weber says social action only those action in which actions are affecting to other person

Types of Social Action: Social action is more important in sociological viewpoint of Weber. Social action is the subject matter of sociology. Max Weber describes the level of sociological action. These different level and type describe the sociological behavior of human of sociological action. Max Weber divided in following four parts the main type of sociological action: [2.4]

Accordingly, teachers can help writers develop teaching writing by providing opportunities and guidance for pupils in social action:

- read texts from multiple points of view (e.g., sympathetic to a writer's position and critical of it) and in ways that are appropriate to the academic discipline or other contexts where the texts are being used;
- write about texts for multiple purposes including (but not limited to) interpretation, synthesis, response, summary, critique, and analysis;
- craft written responses to texts that put the writer's ideas in conversation with those in a text in ways that are appropriate to the academic discipline or context;
- create multiple kinds of texts to extend and synthesize their thinking (e.g., analytic essays, scripts, brochures, short stories, graphic narratives);
- evaluate sources for credibility, bias, quality of evidence, and quality of reasoning;
- conduct primary and secondary research using a variety of print and non-print sources;
- write texts for various audiences and purposes that are informed by research (e.g., to support ideas or positions, to illustrate alternative perspectives, to provide additional contexts); and

- generate questions to guide research

According to the Foundation for Teaching writing by John Chaffee, by enhancing critical

reading and teaching writing skills, we enhance our writing skills.

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